

Method for Evaluating the Probability Functions in Some Contagious Distributions

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Abstract

This paper examines the accuracy of an approximation method for computing probability functions and survivor functions of a contagious distribution. Numerical comparisons are made with the exact results in terms of relative errors for various parameter combinations.

Key Words: Approximation, Contagious distribution, Probability function, Survivor function

1. Introduction

The contagious distributions have been widely used in the study of biology, ecology, entomology, medical statistics, and insurance. A contagious distribution has a probability-generating function of the form $P_X(z) = P_1(P_2(z))$, where $P_1(z)$ and $P_2(z)$ are referred to as the primary and secondary distributions, respectively. For example, if the number of colonies has a Poisson distribution and the number of bacteria per colony is a binomial one. Then, the number of bacteria per entire lot follows a Poisson-binomial distribution. Here, the primary distribution is Poisson, and the secondary distribution is binomial. Section 2 provides a brief description of the approximation method ([1], [2]). Section 3 presents the numerical comparison of the approximations with the exact results for probability functions and survivor functions. The final section contains the conclusions

2. Approximation Method

We first convert the probability generating function of a discrete random variable X to the cumulant generating function, $C_X(t)$, and use it in the approximation method. The approximation to the probability function $P(X = k)$ is given ([2]) as

$$f_X(k) = P(X = k) \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi C_X''(\hat{t})}} e^{\{c(\hat{t}) - \hat{t}k\}}, \quad (1)$$

for integer values of k , where \hat{t} is the solution to the equation $C_X'(\hat{t}) = k$. [1] provided two continuity corrections to the approximation for the survivor probability in order to improve the accuracy.

First Continuity Correction:

$$\widehat{S}_1(k) \approx P(X \geq k) = \begin{cases} 1 - \Phi(\hat{w}) - \phi(\hat{w})\left\{\frac{1}{\hat{w}} - \frac{1}{\hat{w}_1}\right\}, & k \neq \mu \\ \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \left\{ \frac{\gamma_X}{6} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\mu_2}} \right\}, & x = \mu \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{w} = \text{sgn}(\hat{t})\sqrt{2\{\hat{t}k - C_X(\hat{t})\}}$ and $\hat{w}_1 = (1 - e^{-\hat{t}})\sqrt{C_X''(\hat{t})}$.

Second Continuity Correction: Define $k^- = k - \frac{1}{2}$ as the continuity corrected value of k . Then

$$\widehat{S}_2(k) \approx P(X \geq k) = \begin{cases} 1 - \Phi(\tilde{w}_2) - \phi(\tilde{w}_2)\left\{\frac{1}{\tilde{w}_2} - \frac{1}{\tilde{w}_2}\right\}, & k^- \neq \mu \\ \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma_X}{6\sqrt{2\pi}}, & k^- = \mu \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

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where $\tilde{w}_2 = \text{sgn}(\tilde{t})\sqrt{2\{\tilde{t}k^- - C_X(\tilde{t})\}}$, $\tilde{u}_2 = 2 \sinh(\tilde{t}/2)\sqrt{C_X''(\tilde{t})}$, and the continuity corrected \tilde{t} is obtained by solving $C_X'(\tilde{t}) = k^-$.

Third Continuity Correction:

In equation (3), the quantity u_2 is replaced by $\hat{u}_3 = \hat{t}\sqrt{C_X''(\hat{t})}$.

3. Some Contagious Distributions

3.1 Poisson-Binomial Distribution (λ, n, p) :

In this example, the primary distribution is Poisson with parameter λ , and the secondary distribution has binomial with parameters n and p . Figure ?? displays the exact and approximate probability functions and the corresponding survivor functions for the Poisson-binomial distributions with parameters $(\lambda, n, p) = (3, 5, 0.4), (3, 4, 0.5)$. Table 1 presents the absolute relative errors for the survivor probabilities. It shows that the approximation has quite small relative errors for all values of k .

Figure 1: Poisson-Binomial (λ, n, p)

3.2 Poisson-Poisson Distribution (λ, β) :

In this example, primary and secondary distributions are Poisson with parameters λ and β , respectively. Figure 2 presents the exact and approximate probability functions and the corresponding survivor functions for the Poisson-Poisson distributions (λ, β) with two sets of parameters $(5, 3)$ and $(3, 2)$. Table 2 reports the absolute relative errors for the survivor probabilities. The approximation with all three continuity corrections shows relatively small relative errors for all values of k .

Poisson-Binomial (3, 5, 0.4)				Poisson-Binomial (3, 4, 0.5)			
k	$Error1$	$Error2$	$Error3$	k	$Error1$	$Error2$	$Error3$
5	0.002	0.001	0.000	5	0.001	0.000	0.001
6	0.001	0.000	0.001	6	0.001	0.001	0.001
7	0.002	0.000	0.000	7	0.003	0.001	0.001
8	0.000	0.002	0.001	8	0.001	0.001	0.000
9	0.002	0.000	0.002	9	0.001	0.001	0.001
10	0.000	0.002	0.000	10	0.000	0.001	0.001
11	0.001	0.001	0.002	11	0.001	0.001	0.002
12	0.004	0.002	0.006	12	0.003	0.002	0.006
13	0.005	0.004	0.008	13	0.003	0.001	0.006
14	0.000	0.002	0.003	14	0.002	0.001	0.006

Table 1: Absolute Relative Errors

Figure 2: Poisson-Poisson (λ, β)

Poisson-Poisson (5, 3)				Poisson-Poisson (3, 2)			
k	$Error1$	$Error2$	$Error3$	k	$Error1$	$Error2$	$Error3$
15	0.000	0.000	0.000	6	0.002	0.000	0.000
16	0.001	0.000	0.000	7	0.002	0.000	0.001
17	0.000	0.001	0.001	8	0.004	0.001	0.002
18	0.000	0.001	0.001	9	0.005	0.003	0.004
19	0.000	0.001	0.000	10	0.004	0.002	0.004
20	0.002	0.001	0.001	11	0.004	0.002	0.004
21	0.001	0.000	0.001	12	0.005	0.003	0.005
22	0.002	0.001	0.001	13	0.005	0.003	0.006
23	0.001	0.000	0.000	14	0.002	0.000	0.004
24	0.000	0.001	0.000	15	0.004	0.002	0.006

Table 2: Absolute Relative Errors

3.3 Poisson-Negative Binomial Distribution (λ, r, β) :

In this example, the primary distribution is Poisson with parameter λ , and the secondary distribution has a negative binomial with parameters r and β . Figure ?? presents the exact and approximate probability functions and the corresponding survivor functions for the Poisson-NB distributions with parameters $(\lambda, r, \beta) = (3, 5, 0.4), (3, 4, 0.3)$. Table 3 reports the absolute relative errors for the survivor probabilities. The outcomes are the same as in the previous examples.

Figure 3: Poisson-NB (λ, r, β)

Poisson-NB (3, 5, 0.4)				Poisson-NB (3, 4, 0.3)			
k	$Error1$	$Error2$	$Error3$	k	$Error1$	$Error2$	$Error3$
7	0.004	0.001	0.001	3	0.008	0.005	0.004
8	0.005	0.002	0.003	4	0.006	0.006	0.006
9	0.006	0.004	0.005	5	0.007	0.004	0.005
10	0.006	0.003	0.005	6	0.009	0.006	0.008
11	0.006	0.004	0.006	7	0.008	0.005	0.009
12	0.009	0.006	0.008	8	0.009	0.006	0.011
13	0.009	0.007	0.009	9	0.010	0.006	0.012
14	0.005	0.003	0.006	10	0.007	0.004	0.010
15	0.003	0.001	0.003	11	0.009	0.006	0.014

Table 3: Absolute Relative Errors

4. Conclusions

This paper aims to assess the accuracy of the approximation method introduced by [2] for calculating the probability functions and survivor functions of some contagious distributions. The numerical comparisons in Section 3 show that the approximation provides excellent results for all values of k in all examples considered.

References

- [1] Daniels, H. E. (1987), "Tail probability approximations," in *Inter. Statist. Rev.* , 55, 37–48.
- [2] Lugannani, R. and Rice, S. O. (1980), "Saddlepoint approximations for the distribution of the sum of independent random variables," in *Adv. Appl. Probab.* , 12, 475–490.
- [3] Thiagarajah, K. (2017), "Approximate tail probabilities of aggregate claims," in *Inter. J. of Statistics and Economics* , 18, 1–11.